

**OSIYO
TEKNOLOGIYALAR
UNIVERSITETI**

IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№6 - MAXSUS SON

**74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982**

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

Elektron nashr. 153 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-iyunda ruxsat etildi.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Yashil iqtisodiyotning mamlakat makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlariga ta'siri.....	10
Raxmonov Lochin To'xtamishovich	
Orol dengizi mintaqasida cho'llanishni bartaraf etishning barqaror usuli: tabiiy ofat turizmi platformasidan foydalanish.....	14
Axunjonov Umidjon Mahamadumarovich	
Specific tasks of effective information and communication technologies management in the digital economy.....	23
Saatova Lolakhon Ergashevna	
Chuqur o'rganishga asoslangan moliyaviy firibgarlikni aniqlash uchun yondashuvlar.....	27
Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	
AI va big data yordamida sanoat korxonalarida moliyaviy monitoring va budget nazoratini avtomatlashtirish.....	37
To'qliyev Abdirauf Bahodir o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarning ro'li.....	44
Ismatov Zokir Xuvaytovich	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy boshqarish tizimi samaradorligini takomillashtirish strategiyasi.....	48
Kadirov Lutfullo Xalimovich, Elboboyev Hamid Fozil O'g'li	
Ta'lim jarayonini 3d texnologiyalar asosida tashkil qilish va rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	52
Xushbaqov Eshpo'lat Alisherovich, Axmedova Asal Azimjon qizi	
Biosignallarni qayta ishlashda su'niy intellektga asoslangan bashoratlash.....	57
Qarshiyeva Jamila Yashnar qizi	
Shamol dvigatellaridan qurg'oqchil hududlarda foydalanish.....	60
Samadiy Khusrov Abdusalimzoda	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida multimedial ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish imkoniyatlari.....	65
Sodiqova Umida Uchqun qizi	
Совершенствование и внедрение в практику методики когнитивного моделирования, направленной на решение педагогических задач учащихся с помощью современных информационных технологий (ИИ, VR, тренажеры, интеллектуальные системы).....	72
Турсунова Севара Юсуф кизи	
Yashil iqtisodiyot va uni barqaror rivojlantirish.....	78
Anvarjon Barnoyev	
Modern Mechanisms for Improving the Quality of Financial Control.....	81
Umirzoq Rakhmonov	
Zamonaviy o'qitish strategiyasi va metodlari: dasturlashni o'rganish uchun muhitlar.....	83
Mamatova Shirin Faxriyevna, Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning inklyuziv rivojlanishga ta'siri: o'zbekiston misolida.....	92
Saydali Murodullayev	
O'zbekiston universitetlarini barqaror rivojlantirish bo'yicha xalqaro dasturlar va hamkorlik.....	98
Berdiyeva Gulandon Sa'dullayevna	
Образование в цифровую эпоху: возможности модели «перевернутый класс».....	101
Мирзаев Сунмас Амирович	
Pedagogik mahoratni oshirishda sun'iy intellektni texnologiyalarini qo'llash orqali ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtiradigan platforma ishlab chiqish.....	105
Salomov Shokirjon Jalilovich, Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	
Algorithms and software for automatic spelling and grammatical editing of uzbek words.....	114
Daminov Sunatullo Furqat ugli, Eshkarayeva Narkhol G'uzarovna, Boymurodov Farrukh Farkhod ugli	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish.....	120
Mirzayeva Nilufar Fozilovna	
Kompyuter fanini o'quvchilarning loyihalarni o'qitish jarayonida soft ko'naklarni o'rnatish.....	124
Boboyev Shavkat To'rayevich, Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	

Kompyuter arxitekturasini o'rganishni takomillashtirishda mobil o'yinli metod dasturlaridan foydalanish.....	135
Muxammadiyeva Nargiza Boxodir qizi, Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	
Yosh dasturchilarning skratch dasturlash tili ko'nikmalariga elektron ta'lim platformasidan foydalanish bo'yicha dasturlash ko'nikmalariga ta'siri va dasturlashni o'rgatishga munosabat.....	143
Turdiyeva Umida Elmirzayevna, Normamatov Xayriddin Mengniyevich	

SPECIFIC TASKS OF EFFECTIVE INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Saatova Lolakhon Ergashevna

PhD in Economics, Associate Professor

Professor, Department of Information Technologies,

Military Aviation Institute of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Qarshi

Associate Professor, Department of Social Sciences and Digital Technologies,

Asia Technology University

Author's email: lola.saatova@mail.ru

ORCID: 0000-0002-5647-0269

Abstract: This article fully covers the specific tasks of effective ICT management in the digital economy. It also discusses the main stages and directions of information and communication technologies development in the context of global digital transformation, and provides an analysis of statistical data.

Key words: digital economy, information and communication technologies, transformation, state program, effective management, strategy, mobile banking, cryptocurrencies, electronic payment systems, blockchain, artificial intelligence, internet, digital platform.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida AKTni samarali boshqarishning o'ziga xos vazifalari haqida ma'lumotlar to'liq yoritilgan. Shuhihgdek, global raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining asosiy bosqichlari va yo'nalishlari haqida fikr yiritilgan hamda statistik ma'lumotlar tahlili keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, transformatsiya, davlat dasturi, samarali boshqaruv, strategiya, mobil banklar, kriptovalyutalar, elektron to'lov tizimlari, blokcheyn, sun'iy intellekt, internet, raqamli platforma.

Аннотация: В данной статье полно освещены особенности эффективного управления ИКТ в условиях цифровой экономики. Также изложены этапы и направления развития информационно-коммуникационных технологий в условиях глобальной цифровой трансформации, а также представлен анализ статистических данных.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, трансформация, государственная программа, эффективное управление, стратегия, мобильные банки, криптовалюта, электронные платёжные системы, блокчейн, искусственный интеллект, интернет, цифровая платформа.

INTRODUCTION

In the current global processes of digital transformation, information and communication technologies (ICT) play a crucial role in all sectors of the economy. Alongside the digitalization of the global economy, national economies are also adapting their operations to the digital environment. In Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are being implemented to establish and develop a digital economy. This process requires the effective management of ICT and the application of innovative approaches in both the public and private sectors.

The strategy "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030", adopted in 2019, outlined the country's path toward transitioning to a digital economy.[1] The primary goal of this strategy is to create a favorable infrastructure in the field of information and communication technologies, expand digital services, and lay the foundation for sustainable economic growth.

The adoption of the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy marked one of the key steps in the country's digital transformation journey. In accordance with this document, reforms and mechanisms aimed at the effective management of ICT were clearly defined.

In addition, the State Program for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies, adopted in 2020, established specific mechanisms to implement new directions, innovations, and strategies for the advancement of ICT in the country.

These regulatory documents, which contribute to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, form the foundation of state policy and represent significant milestones in the national digital transformation process. At the same time, their development, implementation, and monitoring carry substantial importance.

It is worth emphasizing that in the context of a digital economy, the effective management of ICT has become a highly relevant issue. The specific tasks of managing ICT in the digital economy include:

- explaining the concept and characteristics of the digital economy;
- identifying the challenges and opportunities in ICT management;
- developing efficient management strategies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The digital economy is an economic system based on information and communication technologies (ICT), in which data and digital resources are considered key factors for organizing the economy and directing its development.

In this context, the issues related to the development of the digital economy have been discussed in various scientific works by both foreign and local scholars.

In her article “Main Directions for Improving the Methodology of Using Advanced Information and Communication Technologies in the Statistical Activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Digital Economy Formation”, I.E. Zhukovskaya highlights the main directions for improving the methodology of using advanced ICT tools in Uzbekistan’s statistical sector.

In the practical guide “Project Management” by K.F. Gray and E. Larson, all stages of project organization are addressed, including project strategy development, project identification, network planning, risk management, time reduction, resource planning, project execution, team management, collaboration in design, measurement and evaluation, monitoring project status and progress, and completing international projects.

E.F. Pilipenko and G.A. Belalova, in their article “Modern Trends in a Systematic Approach to Business Process Reengineering”, focus on using systems analysis and systematic approaches in the design of information systems and business process reengineering. They also discuss key principles that must be followed in reengineering and present alternative models of operations, procedures, and interactions.

In the article “Innovation-Technological Matrices and National Strategies of Economic Development” by E.V. Balatskiy and N.A. Ekimov, the authors introduce a research methodology based on the relative labor productivity index and the relative unit cost index for R&D. This methodology aims to construct innovation and technology matrices for a broad sample of countries. It allows for identifying countries that follow a non-traditional innovation strategy characterized by advanced R&D development relative to the manufacturing sector.

In his article “The Impact of Digital Transformation on Economic Processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, S.I. Hashimkhojaev examines issues related to the transformation of the educational process in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan under the conditions of digital economy development.

The article also analyzes the specific features of forming the digital economy in Uzbekistan. The author emphasizes that ICTs today serve as a main driver of economic growth, a support for the development of strategically important sectors, a tool for improving management efficiency, and a crucial condition for enhancing economic competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research analyzes economic and statistical indicators reflecting the development of the digital economy globally and in Uzbekistan. The activities within the digital economy have been thoroughly studied, and a relevant database was compiled.

Based on the collected data, effective use was made of such methods as observation, comparative economic analysis, systematic approach, and logical analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The core characteristic of the digital economy is its encompassment of data collection, storage, analysis, and distribution in digital format. This capability enables efficient management of production and service delivery processes, while also fostering innovation and enhancing competitiveness.

The digital economy operates across both global and local levels, with distinct key directions in each. These include the following:

- The digital economy at the global level comprises four main directions, outlined below:

The first primary direction is digital transformation. Globally, organizations and countries are leveraging digital technologies to modernize workflows, boost efficiency, and create new services. This process extensively utilizes innovative technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, internet operating systems, and other digital platforms.

For example, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), a widely applied metric in finance and business, indicates that global investments in digital transformation reached \$1.3 trillion in 2020. This figure represents an average annual growth of 16% over the preceding five years (2015–2020). Furthermore, the global artificial intelligence market was valued at \$62.35 billion in 2021, and it's projected to reach \$997.77 billion by 2030, with a CAGR of 42%. [2]

The second primary direction is e-commerce. This encompasses the entire process of trading goods and services online. This aspect of the digital economy stands as one of the fundamental trends in global trade, marketing, and service provision.

For instance, global e-commerce volume reached \$4.28 trillion in 2020. This figure is anticipated to increase to \$6.4 trillion by 2025. By 2022, sales conducted through social media accounted for nearly 20% of the global economy.

The third primary direction involves digital finance and banking services. Through the adoption of digital technologies, banks and financial institutions are delivering their services with greater speed and efficiency. Mobile banking, cryptocurrencies, and electronic payment systems are also crucial components of digital finance.

Specifically, among these components, electronic payment systems recorded a global transaction volume of \$4.1 trillion in 2020, with projections to reach \$8.8 trillion by 2025. As for cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin's market capitalization hit \$800 billion in 2023, and other cryptocurrencies like Ethereum continue to show growth.

The fourth primary direction focuses on digital education and healthcare. The integration of digital technologies in these sectors is vital, encompassing online learning platforms, telemedicine, and the implementation of artificial intelligence for analyzing human health.

In particular, the online education market reached \$250 billion in 2020, with an expected growth to \$1 trillion by 2026 (CAGR 17.2%) [3]. The global telemedicine market reached \$60 billion in 2020, projected to expand to \$175 billion by 2027.

The digital economy at the local level features three main directions, detailed below:

The first primary direction is digital infrastructure development. In Uzbekistan, significant attention is being dedicated to establishing a comprehensive infrastructure to advance the digital economy. This primarily involves the construction of high-speed internet networks, data centers, and platforms that deliver digital services.

Notably, in 2023, \$1.1 billion was invested in Uzbekistan for the expansion of internet networks, including the launch of 5G internet waves and the provision of high-speed internet services [4]. A clear indicator of further production expansion and digital infrastructure development is the registration of 2.5 million new internet users in Uzbekistan in 2021.

The second primary direction is the digitalization of public services. The aim here is to provide swift and efficient services to the public, reduce bureaucracy, and ensure transparency by digitizing public service delivery processes. In this context, regarding the establishment of the «e-Government» system, 80% of public services in Uzbekistan were rendered online in 2021. The target was to elevate this figure to 90% by 2023, and by 2025, it reached 100%. Furthermore, with the objective of implementing digital services in the private sector, the share of digital services within the country's private sector increased to 60% by 2024 [5].

The third primary direction involves digital technologies in farming and the agrarian sector. The integration of digital technologies in agriculture empowers farmers to utilize electronic fields, agronomic software, and trading platforms. In 2020, 1500 digital farming platforms were operational in Uzbekistan. By 2025, plans are in place to increase the number of platforms assisting farmers to 10,000. In 2022, approximately \$400 million in aid was provided to farmers in Uzbekistan through digital agrarian services [6].

Based on the aforementioned stages, analyzing the interaction between the digital economy and information and communication technologies (ICT) and their significance in the economy reveals a profound interrelationship. ICT technologies serve as the fundamental basis of the digital economy, and their effective implementation ensures innovation and efficiency across diverse economic sectors [7].

Firstly, data analysis and decision-making are crucial. Utilizing ICT's technological capabilities (systems, platforms, artificial intelligence) for analyzing production and service delivery processes enhances the relevance and effectiveness of economic decisions.

Secondly, the advancement of the internet and e-commerce is paramount. The progression of the internet and the widespread adoption of digital platforms facilitate the emergence of new sectors within the economy. E-commerce enables products and services to be traded on a global scale, providing manufacturers with opportunities to enter new markets [8].

Thirdly, artificial intelligence and automation are indispensable. Artificial intelligence and robotization allow for the automation of work processes and the optimization of products and services within the economy. Innovations in these areas accelerate production and boost economic efficiency.

Fourthly, the application in finance and banking services holds significant importance for every market participant. Mobile payment systems, cryptocurrencies, and blockchain technologies have become key elements in the digitalization of banking services. This, in turn, makes monetary circulation systems more transparent and faster, thereby attracting investments [9].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The research findings demonstrate that we can observe the development stages and key principles of the digital economy in Uzbekistan. Its evolution encompasses several phases, clearly defined through various strategies and documents.

Digital Uzbekistan 2030: This strategy, adopted on October 5, 2020, set the primary directions for developing Uzbekistan's digital economy. Its goals include improving digital infrastructure, digitizing public services, and implementing innovative systems. In 2021, 1.4 million government services were digitized as part of establishing a digital state. This number is planned to reach 3 million by 2025.

State Program for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies: Adopted in 2020, this program established clear mechanisms to promote ICT development in Uzbekistan, support the digitalization of public services, and facilitate the transition to a digital economy. In 2023, 5G services were tested in Uzbekistan, with a full rollout across all regions of the republic expected by 2025.

Investment and International Cooperation: Uzbekistan is actively focusing on international collaboration to advance its digital economy. Platforms are being created to attract foreign investment and technological partnerships for digital transformation. Over \$3 billion in investments are anticipated to be drawn into Uzbekistan's digital economy between 2020 and 2025.

Legislation and Regulatory Frameworks: New laws and regulatory documents have been developed in Uzbekistan to foster the digital economy. These aim to enhance relations between the state and private sectors, ensure information security, and strengthen the use of digital services. In 2022, over 150 new cybersecurity developments and technologies were introduced in Uzbekistan. Investments in this area are expected to reach \$100 million by 2025.

Stemming from these stages, we can identify the following key principles:

Innovation and Competitiveness: The digital economy is built on introducing innovative technologies and ensuring competitiveness.

Transparency and Accountability: Digital technologies are utilized to ensure the transparency of government services and economic processes.

Economic Efficiency: The digital economy aims to boost the efficiency of production and services.

Thus, based on the conclusions and suggestions presented above, the newly formulated stages and key principles for the development of the digital economy can be further refined. This will facilitate conducting scientific research and analyses (forecasts), and enable the creation, expansion, and deepening of educational materials for courses such as "Digital Economy" and "Digitalization of Economic Sectors with Modern Information and Communication Technologies."

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni "Raqamli O'zbekiston – 2030" strategiyasini tasdiqlash va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida» 2020 yil 5 oktabrdagi PF-6079-son farmon.
2. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cagr.asp>
3. <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/valuation/what-is-cagr/>
4. <https://uzsmart.uz/library/view/6125.html> - O'zbekiston Respublikasi Axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalarini rivojlantirish vazirligining rasmiy veb-sayti
5. Saatova L.E. (2025). Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida biznes modellarini shakllantirish <https://www.marketingjournal.uz/post/marketing-jurnali-2025-yil-2-son>
6. Saatova L.E. Approaches to the Formation of the Digital Economy American Journal of Economics and Business Management 2024, 7(11), 1118-1124 <https://www.globalresearchnetwork.us/index.php/ajebm/article/view/3070?articlesBySimilarityPage=11>
7. Suxrobov M. (2022). Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari. Zenodo.org. <https://zenodo.org/records/14801608>
8. Pulatov, A., & Muhammadiev, O. (2021). Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan ta'lim jarayonida foydalanish mexanizmlari. Journal of TSUE. <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/1319>
9. Usmonov, Sh., & Karimov, A. (2021). Axborot kommunikatsion texnologiyalari va raqamli iqtisodiyot. Journal of JDPU. <https://journal.jdpu.uz/index.php/matinfo/article/view/552>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 6-maxsus son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
